

DOI 10.64108/imh.2025.2.2.14

УДК 37.01/.09: 61

SOCIAL STRESS IN CHILDREN AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BAD HABITS. PECULIARITIES OF LEGAL REGULATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTHCAREN. P. Makhlynets^{1*}, M. V. Kokoshko², M. V. Pyuryk³, L. Mytsak⁴¹*Ivano-Frankivsk National Medical University, Department of Therapeutic Dentistry, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine*²*Interregional Academy of Personnel Management, Prince Volodymyr the Great Educational and Scientific Institute of Law, Ukraine*³*Ivano-Frankivsk National Medical University, Department of Postgraduated General Surgery, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine*⁴*Ivano-Frankivsk National Medical University, Department of Radiology, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine*ORCID ID: [0000-0002-1199-8086](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1199-8086), e-mail: makhlynets11@yahoo.comORCID ID: [0000-0002-5753-9061](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5753-9061), e-mail: makhlynets11@yahoo.comORCID ID: [0000-0002-6065-831X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6065-831X), e-mail: mpyuryk@ifnmu.edu.ua***Correspondence:** e-mail: makhlynets11@yahoo.com

Abstract. Learning for children is a necessary stage in the development of personality, which helps the child to more easily acquire the necessary knowledge to further establish the individual. It is difficult for children to adapt to the constant stay at home, to communicate with classmates and friends online, to adapt to the new rhythm of life and the dynamics of learning. Staying more than half of the time at the computer with a layer of psychological difficulties in the conditions of distance learning leads to constant stress and chronic stress. The modern educational system has changed so much in the last two years that the student must constantly adapt to new learning platforms and innovations.

Stress is becoming an increasingly global problem, especially among children, because it negatively affects their lives and health, the progression of bad habits, and in turn, disorders of the dental system. Therefore, it is important to study the problem of social emotional chronic stress in the educational activities of students in terms of distance learning and its impact on the formation of disorders of the dental system.

To reduce the impact of stressors, children use bad habits: sucking fingers, biting nails, pencils or pens, sitting in front of a monitor with his mouth open, despite a positive breath test (presence of nasal breathing), in the same position resting his head on his hands, causing chronic injury in this area. According to many studies, this may be the result of a person's adaptation to existing chronic stress.

Our study was based on a quantitative study conducted among school-age patients who have bad habits (sucking a finger or other objects, breathing through their mouths, resting their heads on their hands while listening to an online lesson) through a secret questionnaire that collected information on the most stressful areas of life and distance learning under quarantine.

The article presents the results of an anonymous survey of 60 patients, which includes periods of onset and progression of a chronic habit, the presence of various stressors, reasons for poor performance. Our results of a secret survey indicate the state of chronic stress of students, their being in a state of social stress due to new living conditions, frequent changes between periods of live communication and distance learning, psychological problems in the family, emotional relief during the habit. Due to the fact that children live in conditions of chronic stress, they lose motivation to learn. They do not get pleasure from it, but in turn seek help in habits that, according to our patients, help reduce the impact of stress on quality of life and their own emotional state. The results of the study explain the formation of adaptive responses of the body to the stress factor and confirm the relationship between chronic bad habits in children under social stress.

Based on the analysis of the current national legislation, the key issues in the legal regulation of healthcare in Ukraine have been identified, along with directions for improving the regulatory framework in this field. International legal standards have been examined. It has been determined that harmonizing national legislation with international standards is a crucial factor in ensuring children's right to healthcare, particularly in the context of social stress and the development of harmful habits. Suggestions for legislative improvements have been proposed, including the development of specialized programs, the integration of efforts by various institutions, and raising public awareness.

Keywords: social stress, chronic stressor, distance learning, bad habits, *the right to healthcare international legal standards, children, social protection of children.*

Introduction. Today, children are the most vulnerable group in society, exposed to stressful factors. Researchers have proven that social stress is an inherent component of everyday life, and in recent years, it has been studied in the context of complex, systematic relationships and its impact on the course or development of pathological conditions [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Frequent exposure to stressful conditions (such as remote learning during the pandemic, isolation at home, rare meetings with friends, and informational pressure regarding infection rates) or experiencing acute stress (illness, the death of loved ones) stimulates the development of harmful habits [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. Stress has become an increasingly global problem, particularly among young people, and has a negative impact on their lives and health [11, 12, 13]. Daily life during quarantine is filled with numerous stressors, both acute and chronic, which may affect the quality of life of patients. Over the past three years, we have often observed emotional instability in children due to prolonged exposure to chronic stress caused by the pandemic.

To mitigate the effects of stress factors, children resort to harmful habits: sucking their fingers, biting their nails, pencils or pens, sitting in front of a monitor with their mouths open, despite positive respiratory tests (showing the presence of nasal breathing), and resting their heads on their hands in the same position, leading to chronic injury in this area. According to the results of many studies, this could be the result of an individual's adaptation to chronic stress [1, 11].

Child Health Protection is one of the key components of societal development, as it is during childhood that the foundation for physical, mental, and social well-being in adulthood is formed. In contemporary conditions, with the growing influence of social, environmental, and economic factors on children's health, particular attention is needed to legal regulation in the field of healthcare, especially concerning children with special needs, such as dento-maxillary anomalies.

Rationale for the Study. Over the past two years, most children have encountered online learning due to the pandemic. The rapid advancement of technological innovations has engulfed humanity and further "shackled" the youth, who are losing the ability to engage in face-to-face communication due to their lives revolving around screens. Children find it difficult to adapt to constant home confinement, the continuous change of learning platforms, and new innovations. Communication with classmates and friends has mostly moved to online formats. Consequently, young people must constantly adjust to the new rhythm of life and the dynamics of learning. Life spent in front of a computer leads to the accumulation of a range of psychological difficulties in the context of remote learning, which, in turn, causes constant tension and a state of chronic stress.

Stress is becoming an increasingly global issue, especially among children, as it negatively affects their lives and health, contributing to the development of harmful habits. Scientists emphasize that harmful habits play a significant role in the emergence of many orthodontic anomalies

of bite or worsen the conditions for treating such patients, yet parents often neglect this fact. It is essential to remember that all habits carry hidden dangers. Prolonged sucking of the tongue or fingers exerts pressure on the palate and dental arches, leading to deformities. Researchers stress that such habits contribute to the formation of open bites, continuous trauma to the front teeth and periodontal tissues, and the presence of foreign objects in the oral cavity can cause chronic infections, which is confirmed by the higher incidence of infectious diseases in the oral cavity among individuals with open bites [9, 10].

We particularly highlight the habitual head position and agree with the views of other scientists who argue that the prolonged systematic placement of the hand under the cheek or another part of the facial skeleton causes asymmetrical development, frequent unilateral narrowing of the jaws, or their shift in one direction or another [9, 10]. As a result, there is underdevelopment of the jawbones, narrowing, and deformation of the dental arches. In the presence of such a harmful habit, a crossbite or deep bite develops. Another common harmful habit is sitting in front of a monitor with the mouth open, even when nasal breathing is intact (positive breathing test). In children with such a condition, open bite often develops.

Research Aim: To study the presence of chronic social stress in children with dento-maxillary anomalies; to explore the relationship between oral habits and stress factors. To analyze the state of legal regulation in the field of child healthcare and ways to improve it.

Materials and Methods. A confidential survey was conducted among 60 students who live in satisfactory social conditions. The survey included questions about the presence or absence of oral habits, the periods of onset and progression of chronic habits, the presence of various stress factors, academic performance over the past two years, and the presence of pain in the cervical spine.

Results of the Study and Discussion. The results from the confidential survey indicate that 98.3% of the respondents are experiencing chronic tension, 75.0% of the children believe they are in a state of social stress caused by new living conditions, frequent transitions between periods of face-to-face communication and remote learning, 48.3% of all students panic over their baseline level of knowledge in the context of remote learning, while 86.6% rate their knowledge level poorly and report a tendency for it to worsen. Additionally, 51.7% of the respondents are afraid of contracting COVID-19, 35.0% mention psychological issues within the family, and 73.3% of the respondents highlight the emotional relief they feel when engaging in harmful habits.

Legal Framework for Child Health Protection. Ukrainian legislation pays significant attention to the protection of children's health, establishing legal foundations and mechanisms for safeguarding their rights. For instance, the Constitution of Ukraine (Article 49) guarantees every person's right to health protection, medical care, and medical insurance. Healthcare is ensured through state funding of appropriate socio-economic, medical-sanitary, and health-promoting programs. The

fundamentals of Ukraine's healthcare legislation outline the general legal, organizational, economic, and social principles of healthcare in Ukraine, regulating public relations in this area. Furthermore, the legislature regulates the care for strengthening and protecting the health of children and adolescents (Article 59). The Law of Ukraine «On Child Protection» aims to ensure the realization of children's rights to life, health protection, education, social security, and comprehensive development. The state (Article 6) provides children with the right to health protection, free qualified medical care in state and municipal healthcare institutions, and promotes the creation of safe conditions for the child's life and healthy development, including proper nutrition and the formation of healthy lifestyle habits.

The Civil Code of Ukraine contains provisions that indirectly affect the protection of children's health, in particular: Article 281 defines the child's right to life, health, and physical development; Article 284 enshrines the child's right to medical care and treatment; Article 285 regulates issues of guardianship and care, including ensuring medical service for children/

The Family Code of Ukraine contains a set of norms aimed at protecting a child's rights to health, physical, mental, and social development. These provisions emphasize the important role of parents, guardians, and the state in ensuring proper conditions for a child's growth and development. To effectively implement these norms, it is necessary to harmonize them with international standards and introduce comprehensive programs for children.

These legal acts create the legal foundation for the implementation of state policy in the field of child healthcare. However, their effectiveness remains insufficient due to the lack of a comprehensive approach to the issue of social stress and harmful habits. Ukraine is a participant in a number of international agreements that establish standards in the field of child healthcare. The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (Article 24) defines the right of every child to the highest attainable standard of health and obliges states to provide access to medical care. The European Convention on Human Rights (Article 8) guarantees the right to respect for private and family life, which includes aspects of healthcare. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Article 25) ensures access to medical services and rehabilitation for children with disabilities. These international documents are important guidelines for harmonizing Ukraine's national legislation.

However, the issue of preventing social stress and associated harmful habits in children requires further attention. Existing laws and programs often do not consider the complex nature of the problem and fail to provide adequate coordination between various sectors

such as education, healthcare, and social protection. To enhance the effectiveness of legal regulation, we propose the following steps:

Develop and implement specialized programs aimed at identifying and supporting children experiencing social stress, focusing on psychosocial support and the development of stress resilience skills.

Ensure the integration of efforts from different sectors, namely by organizing cooperation between educational institutions, medical facilities, and social services for a comprehensive approach to the problem.

Raise awareness by conducting informational campaigns for parents, educators, and children themselves about the impact of stress and ways to overcome it. Improving the legal regulation of child healthcare in Ukraine is a necessary step to ensure their right to health and to harmonize national legislation with international standards. The implementation of these measures will reduce the impact of social stress on the formation of oral habits in children and ensure their healthy development.

Conclusions. Children living in chronic stress conditions lose motivation for learning. They do not enjoy it, and in turn, turn to habits that, according to our patients, help reduce the impact of stress on their quality of life and emotional state. The relationship between chronic harmful habits in children under social stress is explained by the formation of adaptive responses to stress factors [1, 12].

Therefore, when working with patients today, we must take into account their psycho-emotional state. We should consider every patient as being in a state of chronic stress and pay special attention to the presence of chronic oral habits, which are often the root cause of dento-maxillary deformities and frequently hinder the effective outcome of comprehensive treatment.

Prospects for Further Research. A follow-up survey will be conducted with these children after the removal of the chronic stressor.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this study, including financial, personal, authorship, or any other conflict that could affect the research and its results presented in this article.

Financing. The study was conducted without financial support.

Author contributions: N.P. Makhlynets a) conception and design; c) provision of materials for the study; d) collection and synthesis of data; e) analysis and interpretation of results; M.V. Kokoshko f) writing of the manuscript; M.V. Pyuryk b) administrative support; L. Mytsak g) editing of the manuscript.

All authors have read and agreed with the published version of the manuscript.

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UDC 37.01/.09: 61

СОЦІАЛЬНИЙ СТРЕС У ДІТЕЙ ТА ЙОГО ВПЛИВ НА РОЗВИТОК ШКІДЛИВИХ ЗВИЧОК. ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ СФЕРИ ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я ДІТЕЙ

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Резюме. Навчання для дітей є необхідним етапом розвитку особистості, який допомагає дитині легше здобути необхідні знання для подальшого становлення особистості. З іншого боку, це важкий етап у житті молодих людей, які втрачають можливість спілкуватися офлайн, особливо під час дистанційного навчання. Дітям важко адаптуватися до постійного перебування вдома, спілкуватися з однокласниками та друзями в мережі, адаптуватися до нового ритму життя та динаміки навчання. Перебування більше половини часу за комп'ютером створює психологічні труднощі в умовах дистанційного навчання, що призводить до хронічного стресу. Вивчення проблеми соціального емоційного хронічного стресу в навчальній діяльності учнів за умов дистанційного навчання та його вплив на формування порушень зі сторони зубощелепної системи є актуальним.

В основу статті покладено кількісне дослідження, проведене серед пацієнтів шкільного віку, які мають шкідливі звички (смоктання пальця чи чужорідних предметів, дихання ротом, спирання голови на руки під час прослуховування онлайн заняття) шляхом таємного анкетування, яке збирало інформацію про найбільш стресові сфери життя та дистанційного навчання за умови карантину. За результатами досліджень, це може бути результатом адаптації особи до наявного хронічного стресу.

Стрес стає більш глобальною проблемою, особливо серед дітей, оскільки негативно позначається на їхньому житті та здоров'ї, на прогресуванні шкідливих звичок і, у свою чергу, на розладах зубощелепної системи. Тому актуальним є вивчення проблеми соціального емоційного хронічного стресу в навчальній діяльності дітей в умовах дистанційного навчання та його впливу на формування порушень зубощелепної системи.

У статті наведені результати анонімного опитування 60 пацієнтів з наявними зубощелепними аномаліями, де включені періоди появи та прогресування хронічної звички, наявність різних стресових чинників, причин незадовільної успішності. Наші результати таємного опитування свідчать про стан хронічного стресу студентів, перебування їх у стані соціального стресу через нові умови життя, часту зміну періодів живого спілкування та дистанційного навчання, психологічні проблеми в родині, емоційне розвантаження під час звички.

Результати дослідження пояснюють формування адаптаційних реакцій організму на стресовий фактор і підтверджують взаємозв'язок хронічних шкідливих звичок у дітей в умовах соціального стресу.

Висновки. Отримані результати таємного анкетування свідчать про стан хронічного напруження учнів, їх перебування у стані соціального стресу, що зумовлений новими умовами життя через онлайн навчання, частими змінами між періодами живого спілкування, умовами дистанційного навчання та психологічними проблемами у родині, відчуття емоційного полегшення у період застосування шкідливої звички. На основі аналізу чинного національного законодавства визначено основні проблеми правового регулювання охорони здоров'я в Україні та окреслено напрями удосконалення нормативно-правової бази у цій сфері. Досліджено міжнародно-правові стандарти. Визначено, що гармонізація національного законодавства з міжнародними стандартами є ключовим фактором для забезпечення права на охорону здоров'я дітей, зокрема в умовах соціального стресу та формування шкідливих звичок. Запропоновано шляхи вдосконалення законодавства, включаючи розробку спеціалізованих програм, інтеграцію зусиль різних відомств та підвищення обізнаності громадськості.

Ключові слова: соціальний стрес, хронічний стрес, дистанційне навчання, шкідливі звички, право на охорону здоров'я, міжнародно-правові стандарти, діти, соціальний захист дітей.

Стаття надійшла в редакцію 07.04.2025 р.

Стання прийнята до видання 29.08.2025 р.